

Generalized regression models when responses follow family of flexible distributions

Oluremi Abayomi¹, Carl Lee², Felix Famoye²

¹Department of Statistics and Operation Research, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, NC 27599

²Department of Statistics, Actuarial & Data Sciences, Central Michigan University, Mt. Pleasant, MI 48859

Abstract

During the recent two decades, several frameworks were proposed to develop generalized flexible statistical distributions for fitting highly skewed, leptokurtic or platykurtic data distributions. Some noticeable frameworks include (a) skewed symmetric distributions, (b) adding one additional parameter to existing distributions (c) Beta-generated family and its extensions, including $T-R\{Z\}$ family and (d) transmuted family. Some of the generalized distributions have been applied to fit regression models by assuming the responses following some flexible distributions. In this presentation, a framework for modeling the location parameter of response variables following the $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions will be presented. Three types of generalized regression models will be presented, depending on the types of $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions. A generalized distribution based on the $T-R\{Z\}$ framework, namely, Kumaraswamy-Dagum (Kum-D) distribution is derived, along with some properties. A generalized regression model with the response assumed to the Kum-D is derived and applied to model the physical health condition on a list of covariates using the survey data collected in Alberta, Canada.

Key Words: framework, flexible distribution, generalized regression

1. Introduction

Parametric modeling and inferences are important topics in the development of statistical theory and applications. They heavily depend on statistical distributions. The fast advancement of computing technology provides new and innovative techniques for deriving parametric modeling and inferences for responses that do not follow common statistical distributions, such as normal, lognormal, Weibull.

Several techniques have been derived to develop generalized flexible statistical distributions for fitting highly skewed, leptokurtic or platykurtic data distributions. Some noticeable techniques include (a) skewed symmetric distributions (e.g., Azzalini, 1985; Ferreira and Steel, 2006; Aljarrah et al., 2018), (b) adding parameters to existing distributions (e.g., Mudholkar and Srivastava, 1993; Marshall and Olkin, 1997), (c) Beta-generated family and its extensions, including $T-R\{Z\}$ family (e.g., Eugene et al., 2002; Alzaatreh et al., 2013; Aljarrah et al., 2014), and (d) transmuted family (e.g., Aryal and Tsokos, 2009; Bourguignon et al., 2016) For detail reviews of different techniques, one may refer to Lee et al. (2013) and Rahman et al. (2020), and references herein.

Some of the generalized distributions have been applied to fit regression models by assuming the responses following some flexible distributions (e.g., Prudente and Cordeiro, 2010; Silva et al., 2010; Ortega et al., 2011; Famoye and Lee, 2017; Alzaatreh et al., 2021). A popular generalized regression models is the well known generalized linear model (GLM) by defining different link functions on the response so that the relation between the link function of the response and covariates becomes linear. This type of GLM was systematically studied and popularized by McCullagh and Nelder (1989). In GLM, the response variable is assumed to follow an exponential family distribution. The distributions satisfying exponential family may be continuous or discrete. A link function defined on the expected response has a linear relation with the independent variables. Logistic regression is a GLM for modeling a binomial distributed response variable using the logit link function. Log linear model is a GLM for modeling a Poisson distributed response using the log link function.

Many of new flexible distributions derived from the techniques mentioned above are not members of exponential family. In order to build linear regression models, the assumption of GLM is not met. The question is “Is there a systematic method on how to fit a generalized linear models when the response variables are members of flexible family of distributions, in particular, distributions of $T-R\{Z\}$ family?” This article attempts to provide a framework for generating generalized linear regression models for responses derived using the $T-R\{Z\}$ methodology for continuous random variables. The article is organized as follow. Section 2 briefly review the $T-R\{Z\}$ framework for generating flexible family of distributions and defines a framework for generating generalized regression models for responses following the distributions originated from the $T-R\{Z\}$ family. Section 3 defines a random variable generated from the $T-R\{Z\}$ namely Kumaraswamy-Dagum distribution (Kum-D). Section 4 presents a generalized regression model when the response following the Kum-D distribution using the health status data collected from the survey between 2017 and 2019 by Awosoga et al. (2020). Section 5 gives a summary and concluding remarks.

2. A Framework for Generating Statistical Models

In building regression models, the primary interest is to investigate the relationship between the dependent variable and one or more predictor variables (or covariates). Linear regression models assume response variable following normal distribution. When the response does not follow normal, a common approach is by applying transformation on the response using, e.g., Box-Cox transformation techniques, so that the transformed response follows approximately normal. Another popular generalization is the well known GLM by defining link function on the response so that the relation between the expected transformed response has a linear relationship with covariates. In this article, we ask the question “How can we derive a generalized linear model to model the location or scale parameter of the response, Y , which follows the $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions?” Using the unified notation suggested by Alzaatreh et al. (2014) for the $T-R\{Z\}$ framework, The CDF of a random variable Y belonging to the $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions is defined as

$$F_Y(y) = \int_a^{Q_z(F_R(y))} f_T(t) dt = F_T\{Q_z(F_R(y))\}, \quad (1)$$

and the PDF of the $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions is

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{f_R(y)}{f_z\{Q_z(F_R(y))\}} \cdot f_T\{Q_z(F_R(y))\}. \quad (2)$$

Where Q_z is the quantile function of random variable Z .

Let Y be the response and \mathbf{X} be a vector of p predictor variables. The family of generalized regression model for modeling Y on \mathbf{X} when Y following a distribution in the $T-R\{Z\}$ family can be defined as

$$F_Y(y | \mathbf{X}) = \int_a^{Q_z(F_R(y|\mathbf{X}))} f_T(t) dt = F_T\{Q_z(F_R(y | \mathbf{X}))\}. \quad (3)$$

Where $F_R(y | \mathbf{X})$ defines a statistical model for fitting Y on \mathbf{X} , and Y is a generalized distribution of R obtained using $T-R\{Z\}$ family. Based on equation (3), if one can define a statistical model for

R , then, equation (3) defines a generalized statistical model for the response Y where Y is a generalized distribution of R .

2.1 Types of generalized statistical models for Y based on the distributions of R

The generalized models for Y following $T-R\{Z\}$ distributions using equation (3) depend on the types of regression models for R . In the following, three types of distributions of R are defined so that generalized linear models for some functions of Y may be defined.

- (i) Scale-location CDF: Let R be a random variable with CDF $F_R(y)$, which is of the scale-location parameter having

$$F_R(y) = G_R\left(\frac{\Psi(y) - c}{\gamma}\right). \quad (4)$$

where $\Psi(y)$ is a function of R evaluated at some point y in the support of R and c is a location parameter. γ is a scale parameter of the CDF $F_R(y)$.

- (ii) Exponent-log CDF: Let R be a random variable with CDF $F_R(y)$, which is not originally of the scale-location parameter type in (4) but can be linearized using the exponential identity $e^{\ln f(y)} = f(y)$ to form the scale-location parameter type in (4). For example, a Weibull random variable R has CDF given by $F_R(y) = 1 - e^{-(y/\lambda)^k}$, which can be written as $F_R(y) = 1 - \exp(-e^{k(\log y - \log \lambda)})$. We name this type of distributions to be exponent-log CDF.

- (iii) Transmuted CDF: Suppose $G_R(y; \omega)$ is a baseline CDF having the parameter vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_k)$. According to Afify et al. (2016), the CDF of the transmuted class of distributions is defined by

$$F_R(y; \lambda, \omega) = G_R(y; \omega)[(1 + \lambda) - \lambda G_R(y; \omega)]. \quad (5)$$

where $|\lambda| \leq 1$. Suppose further that $G_R(y; \omega)$ is of the type in (4) or can be linearized by using the exponential identity $e^{\ln f(y)} = f(y)$ to obtain scale-location parameter type in (4). Then it follows that $F_R(y; \lambda, \omega)$ can be expressed as the type in (4) or linearized using the exponential identity.

For all CDFs of a random variable R satisfying any of the conditions in (i), (ii) and (iii), a linear regression model based on the $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions can be obtained by fitting a location parameter c or a scale parameter γ in (4) given by

$$F_Y(y | \mathbf{X}) = \int_a^{Q_Z(F_R(y | \mathbf{X}))} f_T(t) dt = F_T\{Q_Z(F_R(y | \mathbf{X}))\}, \quad (6)$$

where

$$F_R(y | \mathbf{X}) = G_R\left(\frac{\Psi(y) - \mathbf{X}'\theta}{\gamma}\right). \quad (7)$$

Table 1 lists some examples of distributions of the random variable R that can be presented as the type in (4).

Table 1. Some CDFs of R and corresponding expressions for $\Psi(y)$, c and γ

Random variable R	CDF of R	Type of CDF of R	$\Psi(y)$	c	γ
Logistic	$[1 + \exp(-(y - \mu) / \sigma)]^{-1}$	Scale-location	y	μ	σ
Cauchy	$(1 / \pi) \arctan((y - \mu) / \alpha) + (1 / 2)$	Scale-location	y	μ	α
Gumbel	$\exp[-\exp(-(y - \mu) / \sigma)]$	Scale-location	y	μ	σ

Log-logistic	$F_R(y) = [1 + (y/b)^{-a}]^{-1}$	Exponent-log	$\log y$	$\log b$	1
Lomax	$F_R(y) = 1 - [1 + (y/\lambda)]^{-\alpha}$	Exponent-log	$\log y$	$\log \lambda$	1
Weibull	$F_R(y) = 1 - \exp(-(y/b)^a)$	Exponent-log	$\log y$	$\log \lambda$	1

3. The Kumaraswamy-Dagum Distribution

A random variable Y follows the three-parameter Dagum Type I distribution if its probability density function (PDF) is given by

$$f(y) = \frac{ap}{y} \left(\frac{(y/b)^{ap}}{\left((y/b)^a + 1 \right)^{p+1}} \right), y > 0, a, b, p > 0, \quad (8)$$

where a and p are shape parameters and b is the scale parameter. The cumulative distribution function (CDF) corresponding to (8) is

$$F(y) = [1 + (y/b)^{-a}]^{-p}, \quad y > 0, a, b, p > 0. \quad (9)$$

When $p = 1$, the Dagum Type I distribution reduces to the log-logistic distribution. The CDF and PDF of the Kumaraswamy distribution are $F_T(t) = 1 - [1 - t^\alpha]^\beta$ and $f_T(t) = \alpha\beta t^{\alpha-1} (1 - t^\alpha)^{\beta-1}$, where $\alpha, \beta > 0$ and $0 < t < 1$. Using the $T-R\{Z\}$ framework in (1) by taking T be the Kumaraswamy distribution, R to be Dagum distribution in (9) and Z to be the uniform (0, 1), then, the Kumaraswamy-Dagum{Uniform} distribution is defined in the following.

Definition 1: The CDF of a random variable Y following the Kumaraswamy-Dagum{Uniform} (Kum-D) distribution with support $y > 0$ is given by

$$F_Y(y) = 1 - \left[1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^{-a} \right)^{-c} \right]^\beta, \quad (10)$$

where $c = p\alpha$, $a, b, \beta > 0$. The corresponding PDF is given by

$$f_Y(y) = \frac{ac\beta}{b} \left[1 - \left(1 + \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^{-a} \right)^{-c} \right]^{\beta-1} \left(1 + \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^{-a} \right)^{-c-1} \left(\frac{y}{b} \right)^{-a-1}, \quad (11)$$

where a and c are both shape parameters while b and β are scale parameters. Special cases of the Kum-D distribution are

- (i) $\beta = 1$, the Kum-D distribution reduces to the Dagum distribution.
- (ii) $c = \beta = 1$, the Kum-D distribution reduces to the log-logistic distribution.

The CDF of Y can be presented as the exponent-log type of distribution:

$$F_Y(y) = 1 - \left[1 - \left(1 + \left(\exp(\log y - \log b) \right)^{-a} \right)^{-c} \right]^\beta. \quad (12)$$

Figure 1 shows the graph of the PDF of the Kum-D distribution for various values of a, b, c and β .

Figure 1. The PDF of Kum-Da distribution for various values of a, b, c and β .

3.2 Fitting generalized linear model for response Y following Kum-D distribution

The equation (10) indicates that one can fit the generalized linear model of Y following $T-R\{Z\}$ by fitting $E(\psi(Y))$ on the p covariates \mathbf{X} as $E(\psi(Y)) = \mathbf{X}'\theta$ and assuming other parameters of Y as nuisance parameters. For the response following Kum-D distribution, equation (10) is given by

$$F_Y(Y | \mathbf{X}) = 1 - \left[1 - \left(1 + (\exp(\log y - \log \mathbf{X}'\theta))^{-a} \right)^{-c} \right]^\beta. \quad (13)$$

where a, c, β and $\theta' = (\theta_0, \theta_1, \theta_2, \dots, \theta_p)$ are $(p+4)$ unknown parameters. These parameters can be estimated using maximum likelihood method. Let $\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_n\}$ be the observed n responses, $\mathbf{X} = (x_{k0} = 1, x_{k1}, x_{k2}, \dots, x_{kp})'$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ be the observed k th observation of the p covariates. The maximum likelihood estimates (MLE) of the unknown parameters can be solved using existing software such as R or SAS. In the following application, we use SAS NLMIXED procedure to obtain the MLE.

4. Application

In this section, an application of fitting Kum-D generalized linear model (KDM) is presented by using a health status data of paid professional caregivers surveyed in Alberta Canada. The health status data were collected from a survey conducted between 2017 and 2019 by Awosoga et al. (2020).

Our purpose in this application is to investigate what health status factors show strong impact on the response variable “Physical health condition of caregivers” using KDM. The dependent variable is the log-transformed Physical health condition of caregivers. The other four health status variables are predictors. Cases with missing data are deleted. A total of 827 cases are used for this modeling. The only demographic characteristic included in the model is “Is English your first language?”. Other demographic variables do not show significant association with the response, therefore, they are not included in the KDM modeling fitting. Table 2 describes the response and predictor variables included in the model fitting.

Table 2. Description of the variables in the health status data.

Variable Name	Variable Description	Measurement scale
Physical health	Physical health describes the physical health conditions of LTC/AL caregivers.	1 (Very Poor) – 5 (Very Good)
Health condition	Overall health conditions of LTC/AL caregivers based on the frequency of incidence of body pains, colds/flu, fatigue or low energy, allergies, presence of sores and skin diseases.	1 (Persistent) – 5 (Never)
Stress	Evaluation of stress levels concerning family, work, relationships, finances, general status, etc.	1 (Very High) – 5 (None)
Quality of life	An assessment of the caregiver's quality of life based on personal life, romantic life, financial needs, co-workers, job, handling problems, physical appearance, etc.	1 (Terrible) – 5 (Happy)
Health behavior	An assessment of the caregiver's health behavior with regards to diets, exercise, medical reviews, alcohol intake, smoking, etc.	1 (Never) – 5 (Persistent)
First language	Is English the first language of the caregiver?	Yes or No

A five-point Likert-scale was used in collecting data from the caregivers. An initial reliability analysis was carried out on all Likert-scale, non-demographic section items. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability statistics range from 0.816 to 0.895. Table 3 gives summary statistics of the health status data. Figure 2 shows the histogram of the logarithm of physical health, which is skewed to left (skewness = -1.0848).

Figure 2: Histogram of the response variable - logarithm of physical health

4.1 Fitting the health status data using KDM and comparison with existing models

In addition to applying the KDM, we also apply three other models for comparison. These are Weibull model (WM), log-logistic model (LM), exponentiated-Kum-D model (EKDM) proposed by Huang and Oluyede (2014). The distributions of the response variables all have the exponent-log type of CDF. The SAS NLMIXED procedure is applied to estimate the MLEs for each model. Table 3 provides the MLEs along with the standard errors in parenthesis as well as log-likelihood, AIC and BIC statistics.

Table 3. Parameter estimates (with standard errors) and fit statistics for regression models.

	Models
--	--------

Parameter	KDM	WM	LM	EKDM
θ_0	-0.5029(0.155)**	-0.0245(0.1455)	-0.7293(0.143)**	-0.5044(0.157)**
θ_1	0.05098(0.0369)	0.081(0.03192)*	0.0588(0.0357)	0.05069(0.038)
θ_2	0.6684(0.0400)**	0.4818(0.02934)**	0.6619(0.0363)**	0.6746(0.0431)**
θ_3	0.2536(0.0364)**	0.2117(0.03331)**	0.225(0.03476)**	0.2565(0.0377)**
θ_4	0.2232(0.0365)**	0.2587(0.03044)**	0.2108(0.0351)**	0.2241(0.0373)**
θ_5	-0.1132(0.037)**	-0.0774(0.0347)*	-0.0965(0.036)**	-0.1146(0.037)**
a	15.4272(3.303)**	8.6572(0.2271)**	13.745(0.3993)**	16.987(11.052)
c	0.6405(0.1806)**	-	-	0.1993(1.759)
β	1.5499(0.5776)**	-	-	1.3637(1.2483)
ϕ	-	-	-	3.1413(27.8874)
Log-likelihood	-526.0164	-549.6504	-545.1145	-525.9400
AIC	1070.0	1113.3	1104.2	1071.9
BIC	1112.5	1146.3	1137.3	1119.1

*: significant at 5% level, **: significant at 1% level

Based on the log-likelihood, AIC and BIC, we found that the KDM is the best fit for the health status data. EKDM comes extremely close in terms of these performance metrics. However, the AIC and BIC for EKDM are a bit larger than those for KDM, which suggests the additional exponentiated parameter may be redundant. The predictor variables “Health conditions”, “Quality of life”, and “Health behaviors”, are all significant predictors of the physical health of paid caregivers. Also, the numerical estimate of each of the regression parameters θ_2 , θ_3 , and θ_4 associated with each predictor variable indicates a tendency for the physical health of paid caregivers to improve with an increase in level of each of these predictors and vice-versa, while holding others constant. The demographic predictor variable “Is English your first language” is also found to be statistically significant. The estimate corresponding of the parameter θ_5 indicates that relative to paid caregivers whose first language is not English, the physical health of those whose first language is the English language is better. The predictor variable “Stress” is significant for the WM, but not for the other three models.

5. Summary and Conclusion

A framework for developing statistical models based on the response, based on some functions of Y derived from $T-R\{Z\}$ family of distributions is introduced. The generalized distribution, Kum-D and some properties are studied derived from $T-R\{Z\}$ family. The Kum-D is a generalized random variable of Dagum, which is the exponent-log type of distribution. The generalized linear model, KDM, is derived. The KDM is fitted to the health status data for paid caregivers in Canada to illustrate the application of KDM and compare with three different models. Performance metrics such as log-likelihood, AIC, and BIC are used for comparison among the four models. The results indicate KDM model the best. Findings from our analysis also indicate that the predictors: health conditions, quality of life, health behaviors, and if English was the first language of the caregiver show statistically significant impact to the physical health condition of paid caregivers for all four models.

References

- Afify, A. Z., Cordeiro, G. M., Yousof, H. M., Alzaatreh, A., & Nofal, Z. M. (2016). The Kumaraswamy transmuted-G family of distributions: properties and applications. *Journal of Data Science*, 14(2), 245-270.
- Aljarrah, M.A., Lee, C., Famoye, F. (2014). On generating T-X family of distributions using quantile functions. *Journal of Statistical Distributions and Applications*. 1(2).
- Aljarrah, M.A., Famoye, F., Lee, C. (2018). A new generalized normal distribution: Properties and applications. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*, DOI: 10.1080/03610926.2018.1483509.
- Alzaatreh, A., Lee, C., Famoye, F. (2013). A new method for generating families of continuous distributions. *Metron*. 71(1), 63-79.
- Alzaatreh, A., Aljarrah, M.A., Almagambetova, A. and Zakiyeva, N. (2021). On the Regression Model for Generalized Normal Distributions. *Entropy* 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/e23020173>.
- Aryal, R., Tsokos, P. (2009). On the transmuted extreme value distribution with application. *Nonlinear Analysis*. 71, 1401-1407.
- Awosoga, O. A., Doan, J. B., Steinke, C., Sajobi, T. T., Murphy, S., Baerg, S., ... & Lucchesi, A. (2020). *Caring for paid professional caregivers: investigating the health status of long-term care and assisted living facilities workers in Alberta*. University of Lethbridge.
- Bourguignon, M., Ghosh, I. and Cordeiro, G.M. (2016). General Results for the Transmuted Family of Distributions and New Models. *Journal of Probability and Statistics*, Vol. 2016, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2016/7208425>.
- Azzalini, A. 1985. A class of distributions which includes the normal ones. *Scandinavian Journal of Statistics* 12:171–8.
- Eugene, N., Lee, C., Famoye, F. (2002). The beta-normal distribution and its applications. *Communications in Statistics-Theory and Methods*. 31(4), 497-512.
- Famoye, F., & Lee, C. (2017). Exponentiated-exponential geometric regression model. *Journal of Applied Statistics*, 44(16), 2963-2977.
- Ferreira, J.T.A.S., Steel, M.F.J. (2006). A constructive representation of univariate skewed distributions. *Journal of the American Statistical Association*. 101, 823-829.
- Huang, S., & Oluyede, B. O. (2014). Exponentiated Kumaraswamy-Dagum distribution with applications to income and lifetime data. *Journal of Statistical Distributions and Applications*, <https://doi.org/10.1186/2195-5832-1-8>.
- Lee, C., Famoye, F., Alzaatreh, A. (2013). Methods for generating families of univariate continuous distributions in the recent decades. *WIREs Computational Statistics*. 5, 219-238.
- Marshall, A.W., Olkin, I. (1997). A new method for adding a parameter to a family of distributions with application to the exponential and Weibull families. *Biometrika*. 84, 641-652.
- McCullagh, P. and Nelder, J. A. (1989). *Generalized Linear Models (2nd Ed.)*. Chapman & Hall/CRC Pub.
- Mudholkar, G.S., Srivastava, D.K. (1993). Exponentiated Weibull family for analyzing bathtub failure-rate data. *IEEE Trans Reliability*. 42, 299-302.
- Ortega, E. M., Cordeiro, G. M., & Hashimoto, E. M. (2011). A log-linear regression model for the Beta-Weibull distribution. *Communications in Statistics-Simulation and Computation*, 40(8), 1206-1235.
- Prudente, A. A., & Cordeiro, G. M. (2010). Generalized Weibull linear models. *Communications in Statistics—Theory and Methods*, 39(20), 3739-3755.
- Rahman, Md. M., Al-Zahrani, B., Saman Hanif Shahbaz, S.H. and Muhammad Qaiser Shahbaz, M.Q. (2020). Transmuted Probability Distributions: A Review. *Pakistan Journal of Statistics and Operations Research*, Vol.16 No.1 2020 pp 83-94.